

ALEKSANDR FAYNBERG CONVEYS ADVISE IN VERSE

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Annotation:The poet is within the culture of the East, and yet, at the same time and in parallel, is the representative and bearer of Russian culture”This, in my opinion, is the main key to understanding why, in the comprehensive concept of the Motherland, it is the East that the poet assigns the main role and thereby creates a qualitatively new voluminous artistic space.

Key words: verse, voluminosity , combination , sequence

In addition, it is not that hard to understand what he wants to say while reading his poetry. When you read his poems, you feel as if he is giving the advice. For instance: let’s consider the poem “ What’s your head stuffed with? ”

* * *

Well, what is your head stuffed with?
Blessed, Miracles do not shine for us
Bears will not roll out honey in a barrel for us
An owl won’t like a swan call us
You dream – as if , Moscow will lift you up.
And the overseas prince will come for you ASAP.
Yeah.

Hereditary.

He'the carriage.

He urgently learns the Russian words.

Take it easy, friend.

Moose don't fly.

And no one carries a miracle in a sieve
not because there is no sieve.

The only exception is poets.

Two miracles open their mouths,
two marvelous divas - vodka and sonnets

In all corners of the halls, his quiet and hoarse voice is heard.

With special trepidation, he treats creative youth, with his light hand the road has opened for many beginning poets.The poem may seen like a simple verse with beautiful rime . However it is not so straightfoward. Aleksander Faynberg wants to awaken us . By writing “ Bears will not role out honey in a barrel for us” means we should work hard as noone is going to do our staff for us either it is not so simple to achieve what we want . In order to succeed , the person ought to work accordingly . Aside from , its mentioned that miracle is not delivered but created . The miracle demands a hardwork.

Tashkent.

1943.

Above David the Shoemaker's Workshop
A newspaper kite hung from the wires.

Heat. Along the stone pavement
Knocks to the beer wheelchair invalid.
Six months since Aunt Lida went crazy.
Waiting for letters from dead sons.
The old man snores at her door,
Looking at the tattered mantle.
Slow summer floats on the rear.
The Father of Nations squints from the portrait.
Beneath it is a closed bakery shop.
Green house.
Shelter of love and faith.
Ranevskaya mined kerosene.
Akhmatova's open doors

In this poem, Aleksandr Faynberg gives the illustration of the Tashkent during the second world war, the feelings of the people and the sequence of the situations are clearly shown. The table of contents of Alexander Fainberg's poetry collections sometimes has numbers instead of the usual headings - 1941, 1942, 1943, 1952. They are partly recognizable.

These are the dates of world history and these are the childhood years of the poet. Time was beating here, and the poet was looking for the main thing for himself in it. Hence the combination in the lyrical hero of a child, a teenager from the past and an adult peering into the past. The author's credo is known - inviolability to "alien thoughts, someone else's anvil, someone else's stubble" and staying within one's own limits - "any field, but mine." Sonnet "Tashkent. 1943" and the poem "1943" about something else, and they are connected by a single common word. In one case, "the rear was snowy," in the other, "a slow summer is floating along the rear." The rear is the wrong side of the war, its reverse side.

A lot has been written about heroism in the rear, but it is remembered less often than feats on the battlefields. They are brighter, more embossed, more emotional, and the "pilot's helmet" on the boy also speaks in favor of military heroics. Plot details - a quilted jacket, a rifle, a disabled person, dead sons - are the result only of the war, but are surrounded by descriptive and psychological details, exclusively everyday. In this routine is the tragedy of the people, horror even in the absence of shots. The poetic plot tells not about one ordinary event, but about the main and only one, about the Event as the essence of the lyrical world. For poems about the 43rd year of A. Fainberg, such an Event is the life of the home front. On a personal level of perception, it is in memoirs created in Uzbekistan by eyewitnesses and peers who did not know each other, but were equally endowed with a literary gift from birth. The well-known People's Poet of Uzbekistan, A. Feinberg's colleague in the writing workshop, translator A. Aripov rightly noted that truly talented people do not belong to any one people. They are the property of all mankind, because, like stars in the sky, they shine for everyone, reflecting the deepest human feelings and eternal enduring values that nourish the Soul. They are able to embody this living, subtle, sharply reacting to everything that happens around the human Soul in an exact poetic word.

A. Feinberg is a poetic phenomenon, a symbol of the era, a multifaceted, deep, multi-level poet, the comprehension and awareness of which is yet to be understood by readers, literary critics and the poets themselves. According to the author of the book "Poetic Mine", Fainberg always

rejected and denounced the prevailing ideological false art and, following the traditions emanating from A. Pushkin and his followers in the 20th century - B. Pasternak, D. Samoilov, Ars.

Tarkovsky, Y. Levitansky, understood poetry as a phenomenon that lives exclusively according to its own internal laws and to the question of its purpose: "So whose is Poetry? A draw, he answered in his verses.

"Guys, I will go to those who have not yet been born...", A. Feinberg said about himself prophetically.

Used literature:

1. https://kultura.uz/view_9_r_6392.html
2. https://45parallel.net/aleksandr_faynberg/tashkent_1943.html
3. https://guarik-guhar.blogspot.com/2014/06/blog-post_12.html?m=1